

Polarized intensity (mJy beam⁻¹)

0.4

0.5

0.6

06 $z_{\text{Sp}}=0.06333$

53°14'

13'

12'

100 kpc

16^h05^m42^s36^s

30^s

24^s

RA (J2000)

Dec (J2000)

